

Research Article

Revitalizing the Tourism Industry of Madhya Pradesh: Opportunities, Challenges, and Government Policies

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Abstract

This paper discusses the status, prospects, and challenges before the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh. It has been observed that there is a huge potentiality of tourism in the State. Madhya Pradesh is known for its eco-friendly destinations and the abundant natural diversity. It is also called as the "Tiger State of India." It is a unique place with rugged mountains, dense forests, deep valleys, raging rivers, lakes and waterfalls. The location of the state is also an advantage for the tourism industry. It is situated in the centre of country. It has three UNESCO World Heritage sites like the Buddhist Monuments at Sanchi, Rock Shelters of Bhimbetka, and the Khajuraho Group of Monuments which are famous among the tourists. The state has many natural reserves and national parks. Pachmarhi, Amarkantak and Shivpuri are the popular hill stations. The state is also well-known for its colourful fairs and festivals. Bhagoriya dance of Jhabua, Ramanavami of Chitrakoot and Orchha, Dusshera in Jabalpur, Shivratri in Khajuraho, Bhojpur, Pachmarhi and Ujjain; and the annual festival of dances at Khajuraho attract thousands of tourists every year. Tourist arrival in the state is growing constantly after the withdrawal of the corona pandemic restrictions. This industry in the state had suffered during the corona pandemic period. Tour operators, traders, taxi drivers, and vendors were the worst suffers during the restrictions. Though there are six tiger reserves, the Satpura Tiger Reserve is the most sought after are widespread tourist destination. October- February are the best time for visitors to travel the state. There are many challenges before this sector of the State. Shortage of infrastructure facilities, fund, and transport facilities are the major challenges. Therefore, the tourism department should implement proper policies for mitigating the constrains so as to develop the tourism sector in the state. The researcher has tried to identify the relationship between the impact of corona pandemic on tourist arrivals and the gross state domestic products through developed hypotheses.

Keywords: Home Stay facilities, Hospitality, Revenue, Tourist and Tourism industry

Introduction

Tourism is a nature based activity that increases the interest of people about certain places. It improves communications among the peoples and solves various social disputes. Local people are benefited through tourism sector without affecting their culture and customs. Sustainable tourism benefits visitors and local peoples (Ahrawa et.al., 171-172). Tourism is useful for promoting nature and culture of the people. India has a number of diversified culture and natural spots which open the opportunities for development of ecotourism. Lakshadweep Islands, North-East India, Kerala, and the Himalayan region have the enormous scope for the growth of tourism sector (Gohil, 72).

Tourism contributes approximately 4.6 percent to Indias Gross Domestic Product. There are 42 World Heritage Sites in India. Out of these, seven are natural, thirty-four are cultural and one (Khangchendzonga National Park) is of mixed type (Kishnani & Sharma, 203-204). There are 34 notified National Geological Heritage Monument Sites in India. Madhya Pradesh is rich in mineral resources. The state is inclusive of Nimar, Gwalior, Reva, Mahakaushal, Malwa, Bundelkhand, and Baghelkhand culture. The state is divided in several agro-climatic zones. It has many communities, ethnic groups and tribes (Jhawar & Jain, 17).

The Study Area:

Madhya Pradesh is a state in central India. It is the second largest state in area and the fifth state of India by area, and population. It has borders with Chhattisgarh, Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, Gujarat, and Maharashtra. It is a land locked state. It is between the latitude of 21.6°N–26.30°N and longitude of 74°9'E–82°48'E. The state enjoys three major seasons, namely Winter, Monsoon, and Summer. It is the tenth-largest economy in India. The state has 55 districts and home of large number of scheduled tribe's groups. Hindi is the official language and Hinduism is the main religion.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objective of this paper is to study the status of tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh. The subjective objectives of the paper are: (a) to study the trends of tourist arrivals in pre-and post-corona pandemic period in Madhya Pradesh; (b) to examine the prospects of

tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh; (c) to evaluate challenges before the tourism industry in Madhya Pradesh, and (d) to identify the initiatives of state government for development of tourism industry.

Hypotheses of the Study:

The following are the hypotheses of the present study.

H₀₁: There is no impact of corona pandemic on tourist arrivals in Madhya Pradesh.

H_{1a}: There is impact of corona pandemic on tourist arrivals in Madhya Pradesh.

H₀₂: There is no relation between tourist arrivals and gross state domestic products in Madhya Pradesh

H_{1b}: There is a relation between tourist arrivals and gross state domestic products in Madhya Pradesh.

Methods and Materials

- **Design and Approach:** This study is descriptive in design and has utilized qualitative and quantitative approaches. Secondary data for the study has been collected from various government reports, website of Madhya Pradesh Tourism, reports from international agencies, research papers, published theses's, articles, etc.
- **Method of Analysis:** To reveal the tourism practices in general and the future prospects in particular, the method of qualitative and quantitative analysis comprising of descriptive analysis, regression analysis, content and text analysis have been performed.

Result and Discussion:

Madhya Pradesh is known as the 'Heart of India'. It is characterized by rivers, mountain ranges, plateaus, plains, and dense forests. The state is blessed with historical sites, rich culture, and diverse wildlife. Lakes are used for irrigation, fisheries, and religious values. The state has a number of natural reserves and national parks. Sanchi Stupa, Bhimbetka Rock Shelters, Khajuraho Group of Monuments, Bhedaghat, and Satpura Tiger Reserve are listed in UNESCO World Heritage Sites. The state attracts tourists for its rich collection of wildlife abodes, cultural centers, religious places, and natural wonders (Tiwari & Padole, 1-2).

Bhopal is the capital and Indore is the largest city of Madhya Pradesh. Rewa, Satna, Sagar, Dewas, Ujjain, Jabalpur, and Gwalior are the other cities. Bhopal is called as the "City of Lakes." Lower Lake and Upper Lake are the popular lakes. Gohar Mahal, Birla Mandir, Van Vihar National Park, Indira Gandhi Rashtriya Manav Sangrahalaya, Tribal Museum, Regional Science Center, Taj-ul- Masjid, and Kerwa Dam are the other tourist attractions. Tourists can also visit places, like Bhojpur Temple, Bhimbetka Rock Shelters, Sanchi Stupa, Jagdishpur, and Beejasan Mata Temple, near Bhopal. Indore is the cleanest city in India. Rajwada Palace, Chokhi Dhani, Annapurna Temple, Mayank Blue Waterpark, Mandu, Shri Omkareshwar Jyotirlinga, Indore Museum, Kanch Mandir, Janapav Temple, and Pipliyapala Regional Park are the famous tourist places in Indore (Singh et. al, 2023).

Table 1: Year-wise Tourist Arrivals in Madhya Pradesh

Year	Tourist		% Share		Rank	
	Domestic	Foreign	DTV	FTV	DTV	FTV
2008	22088927	251733	3.90	1.80	5	12
2010	38079595	250430	5.10	1.40	6	13
2011	44119820	269559	5.19	1.38	6	12
2012	53197209	275930	5.13	1.33	6	13
2013	63110709	280333	5.51	1.41	6	12
2014	63614525	316195	4.93	1.40	7	13
2015	77975738	421365	5.45	1.81	7	11
2016	150490330	363195	9.33	1.47	4	13
2017	78038522	359119	4.72	1.34	8	14
2018	83969799	375476	4.53	1.30	8	13
2019	88707139	327958	3.82	1.04	7	14
2020	23519632	99819	3.85	1.39	8	13
2021	25554067	41601	3.77	3.94	8	8
2022	35848800	204500	2.07	2.38	-	-

Source: Indian Tourism Statistics, 2008-2022.

Table 1 discusses the year-wise arrivals of tourists in Madhya Pradesh. It has been observed that the number of tourist visits had been on rise from 2008 and declined after 2019 due to corona pandemic. Domestic tourist arrival was more than 8.87 crores in 2019, which dropped to only 2.35 crores in 2020. On the other hand, foreign tourist arrivals were 3.27 lakhs in 2019, and it was just 99.81 thousand in 2020. Lockdowns and travelling restriction, due to the corona pandemic are the main factors behind the sudden drop of the tourist arrivals. Therefore, the null hypothesis-1 is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted, i.e. there is impact of corona pandemic on tourist arrivals in Madhya Pradesh.

Rewa is known as the 'Land of white lions' in the world. Popular tourist destinations in Rewa are Rani Talab, Keoti Falls, Chachai Falls, Bahuti Falls, Venkat Bhavan, White Tiger Safari Rewa, Rewa Fort, Purwa Falls, Govindgarh Palace, and Lukeshwar Nath Temple. Satna city always attracts tourists for its heritage, spiritual, and natural sites. Panna National Park, Sharda Devi Temple, Ramvan, Bharhut Stupa, Chitrakoot Dham, Neelkanth Baba Ashram, Maitri Park, Pannikhoh Falls, Madhavgarh Fort, Maharaja Martand Singh Judeo White Tiger Safari and Zoo Mukundpur are the best tourist places in Satna. Sagar is the city that is situated on a spur of Vindhya Range. Nauradehi, Joggers Park, Eran, Bhapel, Abchand, Gadpehra Temple, Atal Park, and Lakha Banjara Lake are the major tourist attractions of Sagar (Sikarwar et. al., 883).

Table 2: Tourist destinations and activities in Madhya Pradesh

Tourism	Places of importance	Facilities
Pilgrim Tourism	Rajim, Amarkantak, Orchha, Sanchi, Bhopal, Chitrakoot, Omkareshwar, Maheshwar, Ujjain etc.	Cafeterias, Day shelters, Budget accommodation etc.
Leisure and Business Tourism	Jabalpur, Raipur, Indore, Gwalior, Bhopal, Khajuraho, Mainpat, Pachmarhi etc.	Golf courses, Exhibition, Evening entertainment, Convention centers, Country clubs, Weekend getaways, etc.
Cultural/heritage Tourism:	Sanchi, Bhopal, Khajuraho, Orchha, Datia, Gwalior, Mandu, Burhanpur etc.	Dormitories, Trekking, Log huts, Camping grounds, Caravans, Tents, Angling, Cruises, Aero-Sports etc.

Source: Final Report, Vol. I – Main Report, Twenty Years Perspective Plan of Tourism for the State of Madhya Pradesh, p.29.

Table 2 discusses the tourist destinations and activities in Madhya Pradesh. There are four tourist circuits are identified in the state. Dewas is the prominent Pharmaceutical Hub. It is known for Jay Maa Tulja Bhavani Badi Mata Mandir, Maa Chamunda Mandir, Kaila Devi Temple, Kheoni Wildlife Sanctuary, and Maa Chamunda Ropeway. Ujjain is situated on the eastern bank of Shipra River. Mahakaleshwar Jyotirlinga, Sandipani Ashram, Kal Bhairav Temple, Mahakal Lok Corridor and Mangalnath Temple are the tourist attractions in Ujjain. Jabalpur is located on the banks of Narmada River. Major tourist attractions of Jabalpur are Balancing Rock, Dhuandhar Falls, Marble Rocks, Rani Durgavati Museum, Chausath Yogini Temple, Dumna Nature Reserve Park, Bargi Dam, Madan Mahal Fort, Tilwara Ghat, and Pisanhari ki Madiya. Gwalior is called as the “City of Temples”. Sas-Bahu Temple, Gurudwara Data Bandi Chhod Qilla, Gopachal Parvat, Bateswar group of temples, Sun Temple, Tomb of Mohammad Ghaus, Samadhi of Rani Lakshmi Bai, Shanishchara Temple, and Chhatris of Scindia Dynasty are the major tourist destinations in Gwalior.

Table 3: Tourist arrivals in Selected Tourist Places in Madhya Pradesh

Location	Arrival 2021	Arrival 2022	Growth 2022 -21	Location	Arrival 2021	Arrival 2022	Growth 2022 -21
Sanchi	1.45	3.88	168%	Udaygiri	0.34	0.78	130%
Pachmarhi	1.30	2.74	111%	Khajuraho	2.42	5.06	109%
Shivpur	6.74	13.66	103%	Indore	26.29	50.51	92%
Bhimbetka	0.84	1.53	82%	Pench	1.23	2.07	69%
Gwalior	2.55	4.02	58%	Bhopal	15.00	23.31	55%
Kanha	1.77	2.53	43%	Bhedaghat	4.94	6.57	33%
Bandhavgarh	1.45	1.92	32%	Panna	4.20	5.28	26%
Dhamnar	0.23	0.28	23%	Madhai	3.40	4.11	21%
Mandu	7.94	8.64	9%	Adamgarh	0.18	0.19	8%
Jabalpur	10.19	10.48	3%	Burhanpur	0.40	0.41	2%
Orchha	1.35	1.33	-2%	Chanderi	0.50	0.44	-12%
Total					94.70	149.73	58%

Source: Economic survey of Madhya Pradesh 2022-23, pp.85-86. Note: Figures in lakh.

Table 3 discusses the tourist arrivals in selected tourist places of Madhya Pradesh. It has been observed that the number of tourist arrivals to these places had increased from 2020 to 2021. The highest number of tourist arrived in Indore, followed by Bhopal and Jabalpur. Total number of tourist arrived in selected places was 94.7 lakhes in 2021, and it had reached to 149.73 lakhs in 2022. So, the growth of tourist arrivals during the said period was 58 percent. Therefore, there is a post- corona pandemic recovery of tourist arrivals in selected locations in Madhya Pradesh.

Satpura-Maikal mountain ranges and Vidyanchal mountain ranges are the majorment ranges in the state. Pachmarhi, Amarkantak, Mandu, Shivpuri, Omkareshwar, and Tamiya are the famous hill stations. Pachmarhi is the highest point in Madhya Pradesh. It is a part of UNESCO Biosphere Reserve. The is home to several National Parks: Kuno National Park, Dinosaur Fossils National Park, Pench National Park, Panna National Park, Ghughua Fossil National Park, Van Vihar National Park, Madhav National Park, Sanjay National Park, Satpura National Park, Kanha National Park, and Bandhavgarh National Park. There are 25 wildlife sanctuaries and 11 national parks.

Table 4: Arrivals of Tourist in Religious Places in Madhya Pradesh

Location	Arrival 2021	Arrival 2022	Growth 2022 - 21	Location	Arrival 2021	Arrival 2022	Growth 2022 - 21
Ujjain	9.6	181.6	1796%	Maihar	57.4	110.1	92%
Omkareshwar	9.0	15.4	72%	Amarkantak	14.2	24.3	71%
Salkanpur	13.9	17.3	25%	Datia	0.3	0.4	24%
Bhojpur	6.2	7.2	15%	Maheshwar	9.7	6.3	-35%
Chitrakoot	59.2	35.7	-40%	TOTAL	179.6	398.4	122%

Source: Economic survey of Madhya Pradesh 2022-23, p.86. Note: Figures in lakh.

Table 4 discusses the tourist arrivals in selected religious places of Madhya Pradesh. It has been observed that the number of tourist arrivals to these places had increased from 2020 to 2021. The highest number of tourist had arrived in Chitrakoot, followed by Maihar and Amarkantak. Total number of tourist arrived in selected places was 179.6 lakhes in 2021, and reached to 398.4 lakhs in 2022. So, the growth of tourist arrivals during the period was 122 percent. Therefore, there is a post-corona pandemic recovery of tourist arrivals in selected religious locations in Madhya Pradesh. Madhya Pradesh award as has been the 'Best State for Adventure Tourism'.

Madhya Pradesh is known for its most enchanting caves. Lakes are a vivid combination of landscape architecture and tamed wilderness. Shahpura lake, Tawa Reservoir, Sharangpani Lake, Moti Lake, and Lower Lake are the popular lakes. Bharat Neer Cave, Lohani Caves, Chota Mahadev Cave, Bandhavgarh Ancient Caves, Udayagiri Caves, Pandav Caves, Saru Maru Caves, Adamgarh Caves, Bhimbetka Caves, and Bagh Caves are the popular caves. Travellers can enjoy Kayaking and boating in Bhopal Lake, Paragliding, and Rock Climbing in the Hills of Pachmarhi, Tiger Safari, River Rafting, Zip Lining in Kerwa Dam, Cable Car Ride in Bhedaghat.

Table 5: Arrivals of Tourist in Selected Monuments in Bhopal

Monuments	2021-22		2022-23		% Growth	
	Foreign	Domestic	Foreign	Domestic	Foreign	Domestic
Badal Mahal Gateway Chanderi	6	11027	51	8637	750.00	-21.67
The palace situated in the fort, Burhanpur	76	31284	165	36808	117.11	17.66
Bir Singh Palace Datia	29	26306	433	42455	1393.00	61.39
Buddhist cave, Dhamnar, Tehsil Garoth	65	24083	65	31137	0.00	29.29
Hoshang Shah's Tomb	107	113132	705	93038	558.88	-17.76
Gwalior Fort	209	203163	3973	274674	1800.96	35.20
Buddhist Caves	1	27260	6	29056	500.00	6.59
Buddhist Monuments, Sanchi	171	118208	3457	266528	1921.64	125.47
Caves Udaygiri Vidisha	42	35530	539	60441	1183.33	70.11
Group of monument, Royal Palace Mandu	92	344821	1027	319046	1016.30	-7.47
Roopmati's Pavilion	55	336231	763	282678	1287.27	-15.93
TOTAL	853	1271045	11184	1444498	1211.14	13.65

Source: Indian Tourism Statics. 2023, pp.138-39.

Table 5 discusses the arrivals of tourist in selected monuments of Bhopal. It has been observed that the number of tourist arrivals in selected monuments had increased from 2021-22 to 2022-23. The highest number of tourists had arrived at Royal Palace of Mandu, followed by Roopmati's Pavilion and Gwalior Fort. Total number of domestic tourists arrived in selected places was 12.71 lakes in 2022, which reached to 14.44 lakhs in 2023. On the other hand, the total number of foreign tourists arrived in these selected places were 853 in 2022 and which reached to 11.8 thousand in 2023. Therefore, there is a post-corona pandemic recovery of tourist arrivals in selected monuments in Bhopal.

Sanjay-Dubri, Panna, Pench, Satpura, Bandhavgarh, and Kanha are six tiger reserves in Madhya Pradesh. Jeep safari is best to explore the wildlife. Betwa River is popular for the River Rafting. Kerwa Dam in Bhopal is popular for a wide-ranging activities. Travellers can enjoy cable ride in marble rocks and Dhuandhar falls of Bhedaghat. Boat Club in Bhopal is famous for boating and cruising. Van Vihar National Park and Indira Gandhi Rashtriya Manav Sangrahalaya are known for cycle safari. Ralamandal Wildlife Sanctuary Trek, Pachmarhi Hill Trek, Tinchha Fall Trek, Patalpani Waterfall Trek, and Chidiya Bhadak Waterfall Trek are perfect places for trekking. Camping is popular for outdoor adventure.

The state has many pilgrimage destinations holy to Muslims, Hindus, and Buddhists. Chitrakoot, Sanchi, Amarkantak, Bhopal, Ujjain, Maheshwar, and Omkareshwar are famous pilgrimage destination. Mahakaleshwar Temple (Ujjain), Bharat Milap Temple (Chitrakoot), Shri Gopal Temple (Ujjain), Karkoeshwar Mahadev Temple (Ujjain), Siddhanath Temple (Omkareshwar), Karna Math Mandir (Amarkantak), Lakshmana Temple (Khajuraho), Javari

Temple (Khajuraho), Narmada Udgam Temple (Amarkantak) are the famous temples. Moti Masjid, Taj-ul-Masajid, and Jama Masjid are the famous mosques. Gurudwara Shri Gwarighat Sahib in Jabalpur, Gurudwara Shri Charan Kamal Sahib in Burhanpur, Gurudwara Shri Data Bandichod Sahib in Gwalior, and Gurudwara Shri Badi Sangat Patshahi Dasvin Sahib in Burhanpur are the popular Gurudwaras. The Great Stupa of Sanchi is one of the oldest Buddhist monuments.

Table 6: Arrivals of Tourist in Selected Monuments in Jabalpur

Monuments	2021-22		2022-23		% Growth	
	Foreign	Domestic	Foreign	Domestic	Foreign	Domestic
Ancient Site and Adamgrah rock shelter, Kalamdi Rasuliya and kishanpur	41	18655	57	17962	39.02	-3.71
Group of Temple Parameshvar shiv and Karan Temple, Amarkantak	133	30981	94	44125	-29.32	42.43
Western Group of Temples, Khajuraho	795	243475	15271	419259	1820.88	72.20
TOTAL	969	293111	15422	481346	1491.54	64.22

Source: Indian Tourism Statics. 2023, p.139.

Table 6 discusses the tourist arrivals in selected monuments in Jabalpur. It has been observed that the number of tourist arrivals in selected monuments had increased from 2021-2022 to 2022-2023. The domestic tourist arrival in selected monuments was 2.93 lakhs in 2021-22, and increased to 4.81 lakhes in 2022-23. On the other hand, foreign tourist arrivals in selected monuments was 969 in 2021-22, and was 15.42 thousand in 2022-23. So, the domestic and foreign tourist had increased during the period were 64.22 percent and 1491.54 percent respectively. Therefore, there is a post-corona pandemic recovery of tourist arrivals in selected monuments in Jabalpur.

Madhya Pradesh Ecotourism Development Board was founded for development of ecotourism. Kheoni Eco Jungle camp in Kheoni Wildlife Sanctuary is popular eco-tourism destination. The cuisine of Madhya Pradesh influenced the Mughals. Travellers can enjoy the local foods. Some of popular dishes are Poha, Indori Namkeen, Dal Bafra, Chakki ki Shaak, Palak Poori, Bhutte ki Kees, Biryani Pilaf, Gosht Korma, Seekh Kebab, Rogan Josh, Mawa Baati, Badkul, Daraba, and Shikanji. There are a variety of suitable accommodation choices to for travellers which meets their taste and budget.

Table 7: The relation between Tourist arrivals and Gross state Domestic Product of Madhya Pradesh

Year	Number of Tourist	GSDP (in crores)
2011-12	44389379	315562
2012-13	43473139	351683
2013-14	63391042	365134
2014-15	63930720	383944
2015-16	78397103	418736

2016-17	150853525	470669
2017-18	78397641	497102
2018-19	84345275	543272
2019-20	89035097	587525

Source: Indian Tourism Statistics. 2020, and report of Planning commission.

Table 7-a: Summary Output

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.572839785
R Square	0.32814542
Adjusted R Square	0.232166194
Standard Error	81400.81312
Observations	9

Source: Calculated by authors.

Table 7- b: ANOVA Analysis

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	22654088372	22654088372	3.418921301	0.106918771
Residual	7	46382646642	6626092377		
Total	8	69036735014			

Source: Calculated by authors.

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	308487.2634	74646.46889	4.132643753	0.004389421
Number of Tourist	0.001662195	0.000898954	1.849032531	0.106918771

Source: Calculated by authors.

Table (7-a) shows that R square is found to be 0.32814542, showing, that the degree of relation between the independent variable X, i.e. arrivalsof tourists, and the dependent variable Y, i.e. weak gross domestic product. Table (7-b) shows that p value (0.1069) is higher than critical value at the 5% level of significance ($p > 0.05$), therefore the null hypothesis 2 is accepted. So, it is concluded that there is no relation between tourist arrivals and the gross domestic product of Madhya Pradesh. The state tourism department is working for development of adventure, recreational activities and water sports activities at tourist locations to increase the footfall of tourists in the state. October to December period is the peak time for tourism industry. The state government efforts to upsurge the film tourism through its one-window application policy.

The Madhya Pradesh Film Tourism Policy 2020 was implemented to develop of film tourism. The Madhya Pradesh Tourism Board has introduced Home Stay establishment schemes like Gram Stay Establishment (Registration and Regulation) Scheme 2019, Bed and Breakfast Establishment (Registration and Regulation) Scheme 2019, Homestay Establishment (Registration and Regulation) Scheme 2010 and Farm stay Establishment (Registration and Regulation) Scheme 2019. Madhya Pradesh Tourism department organise cultural events to promote various interesting aspects. In the financial year 2022/23, the tourism department had

generated revenue worth Rs. 220 crore. The tourism sector is a growing sector in Madhya Pradesh. It is contributing to the employment and economy of the state. The SWOT analysis method has been used to discuss the current overview of tourism sector of Madhya Pradesh.

Table 8: SWOT Analysis of Tourism Industry in Madhya Pradesh

Strengths	Weaknesses
Rich history and heritage Scenic beauty of the nature Unique culture Salubrious and pollution free environment Socially stable state Hospitable people	Lack of fund for development Lack of transparency in policies Insufficient transport facilities Lack of adequate infrastructural support Inadequacy of infrastructure Lack of proper rule and regulations
Opportunities	Challenges
Adventure sports and trekking. Eco- tourism is gaining popularity Increased disposable incomes of people	Environmental factors Stiff competition from other states Increase in crime

Conclusion:

Madhya Pradesh is blessed with an undulating topography, gushing springs, exotic flora and fauna, sub-tropical forests, waterfalls and misty mountains. This is the perfect place for adventure tourism, it has the provisions for as rock climbing, water sports, caving (spelunking), trekking, and hiking and speed boating. Still the state has more opportunities for ecotourism, adventure tourism, cultural tourism, and agri-tourism. There are scopes of hard and soft tourism activities. Tourists can use the homestay as well as homely stay in local resorts. Travellers can involve in dances, campfires, meeting animals, breweries etc. Though there is a bright future for tourism industry in the state, transportation, tourist facilities, hygienic food, accommodation, tourist information system, brand image etc. are the basic challenges before this sector.

Direct and indirect tourism contribute to the economy. It generates employment, increases income, adds to government revenue, through foreign exchange, helps in infrastructure building and so on. It has a variety of ecosystems, landscapes, and wildlife. Homestays with the locals are popular among the tourists. Adventurous activities, jungle safari, trekking, pilgrimage tour, mountaineering, tea garden tour, ornithological tour etc. have opened a massive scope for the tourist. The ethnic landscape is useful for other tourism like mountain tourism. folklore tourism tribal tourism, anthropological tourism, tea tourism, and ethnic tourism. Transportation, accessibility, tourist facilities, hygienic food, accommodation, tourist information system, system of permit, brand image etc. are the basic challenges before the tourism industry. Implementation of proper tourism polices are important for the development of this industry.

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